

TRADITIONAL-BASED LEARNING VERSUS PHENOMENON-BASED LEARNING

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Abstract:

Currently, it has been observed that students mostly wait for the instructions of teachers. A teacher explains the planned topic and correspondingly he or she gives questions to clarify whether students understood the topic. After that students will be asked to find additional information regarding the topic. The whole process will be based on rote memorization of facts which will hardly make students go further to investigate the topic. It is also observed that after studying the topic, students tend to forget the learned material and hardly apply it in their everyday life. The current article compares the traditional learning methods with the Phenomenon-based learning approach by demonstrating the limitations and strengths of the two approaches. It also presents Bloom's Taxonomy to evaluate learners' knowledge and skills.

Key words: phenomenon-based learning, cognitive skills, Bloom's Taxonomy, knowledge construction, contextualization

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Concerning the physical environment of learning, it may not go beyond the borders of a traditional classroom. As the research paper intends to investigate the implementation of phenomenon-based learning for EFL students to develop their cognitive and research skills, it will be logical to provide a content comparison of the two approaches further. According to the syllabus of the 2023-2024 academic year for integrated language skills, students are supposed to acquire an overall forty-two topics in the first term. The second term involves thirty-six topics. All the themes are planned to be carried out in the traditional classroom. Further, three of the topics involved in Integrated Language Skills will be presented:

1.	Urbanization and climate change
2.	The world around us
3.	Our endangered world

For each topic, two hours are allocated for class teaching. All three themes will be presented in a classroom devoid of topic relevancy. There appears a reasonable question. If the theme concerns Urbanisation and climate change, why should it be carried out in a classroom that has no relevance to the intended topic? Will this physical environment encourage students to be interested in investigating those topics further?

Another matter of concern is its objectives. In integrated language skills, the main objectives involve the development of learners' language skills, both receptive and productive skills, and the acquisition of lesson material. However,

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excelling in all these skills may not be enough to trigger learners to develop cognitive skills(reasoning, perception, analytical thinking, memory, verbal, problem solving) and research skills (task definition, information seeking, location /access, use of information, synthesis, evaluation) as well as XXI century skills(learning and innovation skills, digital literacy skills, career and life skills) which can be considered to be prerequisites of students' future career life.

According to Bloom's taxonomy, the levels of thinking should involve six steps.

In traditional lessons designed for the development of language skills, a teacher is regarded as a provider of information, whereas students are seen as listeners and respondents. In most cases, it is the responsibility of teachers to maintain the attention of students, by delivering the main points of the lesson of the lesson, and manifesting the topic through textbooks and lectures as a static body of knowledge [Lee, 2020]. A traditional language skills development lesson commences with the objective of the lesson being presented by the teacher. Further, the teacher presents the topic vocabulary and content relevant to the topic to help students a clear picture of the topic. The students then engage in an activity to help reinforce the topic content with a gradual set of activities usually created by the textbook company or the teacher. The students follow these directions and complete a worksheet with questions that may include matching definitions with appropriate vocabulary, explaining what happened in each step of the activity, or regurgitating facts learned from the teacher or reading the textbook [Mancuso: 2017]. Through this process, students do, indeed, learn topic information, but the topic may not always make sense [Capps & Crawford: 2013].

For the last few years, the theme explanation has started to involve more hands-on activities. Hands-on theme explanation frequently attracts students to do collaborative, fast-moving, and quick-thinking activities in the classroom. Many language skills development lessons such as the Integrated Language Skills course in Higher Education have adopted complete curricula of hands-on activities to effectively substitute the use of theme-based textbooks. The hands-on activities provide students with opportunities to apply the presented vocabulary or content in an activity with a specific time framework. After that, students can be assigned to find additional material pertinent to the topic or

learn the explained topic in which students are required to memorize the specific vocabulary or content.

Despite these new hands-on programs being full of fun and informative and having the student learners more involved, they were once again not made applicable to the real world [Moscovici & Nelson: 1998]. Educational research has shown that both the traditional programs with lectures (i.e., presenting facts while students listen) and traditional hands-on cookbook labs (which are defined as labs that contain explicit instructions in a step-by-step procedure that choreograph each action taken by the learner; e.g., “do this,” “measure that,” “record this,” “come to this answer,”) revealed that in many programs are not the most effective ways for students to learn and to retain what they are taught [Symeonidis & Schwarz:2016].

Involving students in inquiry-based learning can be an effective way of facilitating their learning experience. This approach not only helps them acquire knowledge about a particular topic but also helps them develop reasoning and critical thinking skills. Through inquiry-based learning, students learn how to tackle problems by asking meaningful questions and using well-thought-out procedures to evaluate and generate solutions. [Krajcik:2014].

Considering the assessment process, students’ language skills, such as speaking and writing are assessed based on the extent of theoretical knowledge they remember. Again three levels of Bloom’s taxonomy can be covered, including to a great extent remembering, understanding, to the least extent applying it in new situations. The assessment process gives little or no attention to the progress of higher-order thinking skills.

However, Phenomenon-based learning is completely different in content. It is asked not only to understand the presented phenomena but to perceive and act concerning the world. Moreover, students can see, feel, observe, and experience the phenomenon to be investigated as well as it is possible to use scientific information to explain. This process will, in turn, trigger their interest in the topic by stimulating them to ask questions. The process of exploration and investigation is seen as the essence of phenomenon-based learning. Students can be involved in collaborative, communicative, critical thinking, and problem-solving environments. Here, not the teachers but students will ask questions and ultimately be considered to be self-drivers of their knowledge. This approach pays attention to the student's understanding of a phenomenon – an observable event – while using various methods and perspectives that overlap to make sense of this phenomenon [Wakil: 2019].

Phenomenon-based teaching is based on the constructivism theory introduced by Piaget in 1969. According to constructivism, learners are active in building knowledge as they try to make sense of their experiences. This theory is closely linked to elementary students' learning through relevant phenomena. Constructivism suggests that learners create new knowledge based on their past experiences and prior knowledge, which shapes their interpretations and experiences of the world around them. Ertmer and Newby [2013] further argue that humans’ creating knowledge and meaning is an essential part of learning instead of simply acquiring it.

The concept of phenomenon-based learning traces back to Vygotsky's social constructivism learning theory. As per this theory, learners create knowledge by drawing on their experiences. Learning is a collaborative process, and all aspects of the student are interlinked. Vygotsky believed that learning involves co-constructing the meaning of both content and practices with the help of others,

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including teachers and peers. His theory stresses the importance of social interaction in cognitive development, highlighting the community's central role in meaning-making.

Unlike the traditional education model, where teachers are the sole providers of information, Vygotsky's theory calls for active learning. It proposes a classroom environment where teachers and students work together to facilitate meaning construction, fostering learning. Ultimately, these theories suggest that students learn most efficiently by actively creating their experiences and socially constructing knowledge in groups while engaging in questioning.

Several specific components align with the use of phenomena in the classroom, based on various theories. These components include actively constructing knowledge while building background, providing meaningful learning in a collaborative setting, and offering relevant, real-world applications.

The main objective of phenomenon-based learning is students' wish to figure out what is happening with the phenomena by not only giving low-order questions, such as what, who, and when, but also high-order questions, including why, how, or what if. Students will be able to answer why they need to know the topic. They also try to explain what is going on with the phenomenon. All those explanations are elaborated and evidence-based accounts that require young learners to draw upon a wide range of science concepts and to engage in multiple investigations to construct narratives and representations for the target phenomenon.

Figure 1.

Traditional lesson vs Phenomenon-based learning lesson

Traditional language skills development instruction	Phenomenon-based learning language classroom
Introduction of the topic	Introduction of the phenomenon in the real context through observable environment
Explanation	Search to find answers
Questions are given mostly by teachers	Questions are given mostly by students
Fact memorization	Knowledge construction
A teacher is the source of information	Engagement in multiple investigations to construct narratives and representations
Students listen and respond	Explanations are evidence-based accounts

Figure 2.

The phenomenon-based learning process

From Figure 2, it is clear that the phenomenon-based learning process involves seven steps. The first step commences with the observation of the target phenomenon which naturally awakens learners' curiosity and intrinsic interest to investigate it. The curiosity and interest are reflected in learners' questions either formed in low-order question forms (when, who, where) or higher-order question forms (what, why, how, what if). The natural questioning process will ultimately lead to the exploration and investigation of the phenomenon thereby learners can observe, analyze, and evaluate it. Based on observation, analyses, and evaluation, it is possible to make findings of their own finally having the content of their knowledge construction. Rather than relying on others' knowledge, they will be able to construct their knowledge and become knowledge owners. The appreciation of this knowledge is higher than others' knowledge.

The phenomenon-based classroom is considered to be a learner-centered, interdisciplinary instructional approach that is based on student inquiry and problem-solving. There are five primary characteristics of phenomenon-based learning [Symeonidis & Schwarz: 2016]:

1. **Real-world implementation:** The real world is the foundation of phenomenon-based learning. This is always the starting point and is repeated at every stage [NSTA: 2014]. Students and teachers choose to focus on real-world phenomena; such as why elderly people do choose to live in nursing homes. In the classroom, they may give their hypotheses. To check this, they are brought to retired houses where they can check their hypotheses for correctness and ask other interested questions. In this case, they can form their knowledge based on the exposure to the real-world implementation.

Students can learn a phenomenon that interests them and use scientific inquiry and problem-solving skills to understand it and demystify it (Silander, 2015).

2. **Desire to give questions:** Phenomenon-based learning may stimulate students' curiosity, and so students are encouraged to ask questions that interest them [Bendici: 2019; Mancuso: 2017]. This is very similar to the Socratic Method. The Socratic Method incorporates other preferred methods of instruction such as the case method, lecture, and small groups [Plato & Saunders: 1987]. The Socratic Method, as defined by the American Heritage Dictionary of English Language, is a pedagogical technique that involves the teacher asking a series of questions instead of giving direct information. The goal is to help students arrive at the desired knowledge by answering these questions or gaining a deeper understanding of the limits of their knowledge. This approach is similar to Phenomenal-based learning, which focuses on inspiring students to make observations and ask questions by prioritizing "how" over "why." [Inouye:2020].

3. **Contextualization:** Phenomenon-based learning builds pertinent connections between curriculum theory and the real world, but it also serves to link the various, separate subjects that students learn in Higher Education [Chin & Brown: 2000; Odden & Russ: 2019]. For example, the topic of Art appreciation can combine the subjects of Art, Design, and Psychology with integrated language skills. By allowing students to reflect on themselves, they may be given the task of creating art pieces. Through those artworks regardless of their simplicity, students can present their inner world as well as reflect on it orally or in written versions in which they can develop their language skills. The topic of space travel presented in the Integrated Language Course may also incorporate several subjects into one such as astronomy, physics, mathematics,

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and language skills. In this case, the students may be taken to a field trip to NASA where the students can see the phenomenon in a real context. Naturally, they are more inclined to investigate it in an authentic environment rather than in a traditional classroom. Real-world phenomena provide the starting point for learning. Phenomenon-based instruction begins with observing real-world phenomena and leads to a class discussion [Roth: 2014].

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